

Supplementary material

Crisis response and preparedness for Rare Disease populations: Lessons learnt and recommendations by the European Reference Networks

Supplementary table 1. Overview of documents developed by European Reference Networks during the COVID-19 crisis.

ERN	Type	Title	Link
Endo-ERN	List of resources	1. COVID-19 country specific initiatives. 2. COVID-19 European initiatives.	1. https://endo-ern.eu/covid-19/country/ 2. https://endo-ern.eu/covid-19/european-initiatives/
Endo-ERN	Peer-reviewed publications	1. Adrenal function in relation to cytokines and outcome in non-critically ill patients with COVID-19. ¹ 2. Paradoxical low severity of COVID-19 in Prader-Willi syndrome: data from a French survey on 647 patients. ² 3. Outcome of COVID-19 infections in patients with adrenal insufficiency and excess. Endocrine Connections. ³ 4. A critical evaluation of the EU-virtual consultation platform (CPMS) within the European Reference Network on Rare Endocrine Conditions. ⁴ 5. Clinical management of patients with genetic obesity during COVID-19 pandemic: position paper of the ESE Growth & Genetic Obesity COVID-19 Study Group and Rare Endo-ERN main thematic group on Growth and Obesity. ⁵	1. https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-023-02189-y 2. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-021-01949-4 3. https://doi.org/10.1530/EC-22-0416 4. https://doi.org/10.1530/EC-22-0281 5. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12020-021-02619-y
ERKNet	Peer-reviewed publications	1. COVID-19 in children treated with immunosuppressive medication for kidney diseases. ⁶ 2. The severity of COVID-19 in children on immunosuppressive medication. ⁷	1. https://doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2020-320616 2. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30145-0
ERN BOND	Peer-reviewed publications	1. Providing high-quality care remotely to patients with rare bone diseases during COVID-19 pandemic. ⁸ 2. The line between COVID-19 pandemic and rare bone diseases. ⁹	1. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-020-01513-6 2. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11845-020-02400-6
ERN EpiCARE	Recommendations	COVID-19 and epilepsy – ERN EpiCARE recommendations.	https://epi-care.eu/covid-19-and-epilepsy-ern-epicare-recommendations/
ERN EpiCARE	List of resources	COVID-19 information for clinicians.	https://www.ilae.org/patient-care/covid-19-and-epilepsy/for-clinicians
ERN eUROGEN	List of resources	COVID-19: eUROGEN statement and resources.	https://eurogen-ern.eu/covid-19/
ERN eUROGEN	Recommendations	EAU COVID-19 rapid reaction recommendations.	https://eurogen-ern.eu/covid19-rapid-reaction-recommendations/
ERN eUROGEN	Webinar	ERN eUROGEN & EAU webinar: COVID-19 & urology.	https://eurogen-ern.eu/ern-eurogen-eau-webinar-covid-19-urology/
ERN EURO-NMD	List of resources	COVID	https://ern-euro-nmd.eu/?s=covid
ERN EURO-NMD	Survey	Results of survey: COVID19 hospital feedback.	https://ern-euro-nmd.eu/news/results-of-survey-covid19-hospital-feedback/?highlight=covid+survey
ERN EURO-NMD	Peer-reviewed publication	Telemedicine in neuromuscular diseases during COVID-19 pandemic: ERN-NMD European survey. ¹⁰	https://doi.org/10.3233/JND-221525
ERN GUARD-Heart	Peer-reviewed publications	1. Hyperinflammatory shock in children during COVID-19 pandemic. ¹¹ 2. Kawasaki-like disease: emerging complication during the COVID-19 pandemic. ¹² 3. SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, and inherited arrhythmia syndromes. ¹³ 4. COVID-19 vaccination in patients with long QT syndrome. ¹⁴ 5. European Society of Cardiology guidance for the diagnosis and management of cardiovascular disease during the COVID-19 pandemic: part 1-epidemiology, pathophysiology, and diagnosis. ¹⁵ 6. ESC guidance for the diagnosis and management of cardiovascular disease during the COVID-19 pandemic: part 2-care pathways, treatment, and follow-up. ¹⁶	1. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31094-1 2. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31129-6 3. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2020.03.024 4. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hroo.2022.07.011 5. https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab697 6. https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab696

ERN PaedCan	Peer-reviewed publications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Impact of the COVID pandemic on survivors of childhood cancer and survivorship care: lessons for the future.¹⁷ 2. The Global Impact of COVID-19 on Childhood Cancer Outcomes and Care Delivery - A Systematic Review.¹⁸ 3. Impacts of COVID-19 on caregivers of childhood cancer survivors.¹⁹ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-021-06788-4 2. https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.869752 3. https://doi.org/10.1002/psc.28943
ERN ReCONNET	Poster recommendation	ERN ReCONNET posters and endorsed recommendations on systemic autoimmune diseases and vaccines.	https://reconnet.ern-net.eu/covid-19-ern-reconnet/
ERN ReCONNET	Peer-reviewed publications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Long-term outcomes of COVID-19 vaccination in patients with rare and complex connective tissue diseases: The ERN-ReCONNET VACCINATE study.²⁰ 2. ERN ReCONNET points to consider for treating patients living with autoimmune rheumatic diseases with antiviral therapies and anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibody products.²¹ 3. Shaping the Future of Rare Diseases after a Global Health Emergency: Organisational Points to Consider.²² 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtauto.2023.100221 2. https://doi.org/10.55563/clinexprheumatol/jpargp 3. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228694
ERN RITA	Webinar	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pediatric inflammatory multisystem syndrome (PIMS) in the context of COVID-19. 2. COVID-19 vaccination for primary immunodeficiencies & rare autoimmune rheumatic diseases 3. Cytokine storm syndromes, including comments on COVID-19/MISC/LongCOVID 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OYDqY1W2YvU 2. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tI8ejmUySwo 3. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yjsKt6hBaLY
ERN RITA	Peer-reviewed publication	The HyperPed-COVID international registry: Impact of age of onset, disease presentation and geographical distribution on the final outcome of MIS-C. ²³	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2024.103265
ERN TRANSPLANT-CHILD	Webinar	A webinar on 23 June on “COVID-19 and transplantation in children” in collaboration with ERN Transplant-Child.	https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7d70c844-f923-4986-9fe0-95b2cea348cb_en
ERN TRANSPLANT-CHILD	Filmed interviews	Situation during COVID-19: interviews with our health professionals.	https://transplantchild.eu/situation-during-covid-19-interviews-with-our-health-professionals/
ERN TRANSPLANT-CHILD	Peer-reviewed publication	Pediatric transplantation in Europe during the COVID-19 pandemic: Early impact on activity and healthcare. ²⁴	https://doi.org/10.1111/ctr.14063
ERN-EuroBloodNet	List of peer-reviewed publications	Disease groups research.	https://eurobloodnet.eu/research/disease-group-research/
ERN-EuroBloodNet	List of resources	COVID-19 and rare haematological diseases.	https://eurobloodnet.eu/covid/covid-19-information/
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Collaborative platform	ERN-EuroBloodNet collaborative platform on red blood cell and COVID-19 patients.	https://eurobloodnet.eu/covid/access-to-the-platform/
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Online training	Provision of Training on Intensive Care Medicine Skills for Health Professionals Not Regularly Working on Intensive Care Units – COVID-19 Skills Preparation Course	https://eurobloodnet.eu/news/160/the-european-commission-together-with-the-european-society-of-intensive-care-medicine-are-supporting-the-eu-healthcare-systems-and-clinicians-dealing-with-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-the-front-line
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Webinar	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sickle cell disease patients and parents’ patients educational session at ASCAT 2020, a joint project of ERN-EuroBloodNet, ASCAT and BSH 2. SCD patients’ educational session at ASCAT 2020: webinar on COVID-19 pandemic 3. SCD patients’ educational session at ASCAT 2020: COVID-19 pandemic patient testimonies from France 4. SCD patients’ educational session at ASCAT 2020: COVID-19 pandemic patient testimonies from Cyprus 5. SCD patients’ educational session at ASCAT 2020: COVID-19 pandemic patient testimonies from UK 6. SCD patients’ educational session at ASCAT 2020: COVID-19 pandemic patient testimonies from Portugal 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://eurobloodnet.eu/news/168/sickle-cell-disease-patients-and-parents-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-a-joint-project-of-ern-eurobloodnet-ascat-and-bsh 2. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/educational-material/77/scd-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-webinar-on-covid-19-pandemic 3. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/educational-material/66/scd-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-covid-19-pandemic-patient-testimonies-from-france 4. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/educational-material/63/scd-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-covid-19-pandemic-patient-testimonies-from-cyprus 5. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/educational-material/64/scd-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-covid-19-pandemic-patient-testimonies-from-uk 6. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/educational-material/65/scd-patients-educational-session-at-ascat-2020-covid-19-pandemic-patient-testimonies-from-portugal

		7. SCD and COVID-19 8. ERN-EuroBloodNet webinars for patients: risk and course of COVID-19 in AA and PNH patients, including vaccination strategies 9. Vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis (VITT)	7. https://eurobloodnet.eu/patientsadvocacy/webinar-scd-and-covid-19/ 8. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education-2/patients/webinars/patients-webinars/risk-and-course-of-covid-19-in-aa-and-pnh-patients/ern-eurobloodnet-webinars-for-patients-risk-and-course-of-covid-19-in-aa-and-pnh-patients-including-vaccination-strategies/ 9. https://eurobloodnet.eu/education/thursdays-webinars/25/vaccine-induced-immune-thrombocytopenia-and-thrombosis-vitt
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Peer-reviewed publication	COVID- 19 in patients affected by red blood cell disorders, results from the European registry ERN-EuroBloodNet. ²⁵	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-025-03683-7
ERN-EYE (coordinator)	Recommendations	Summary of the view of all ERNs on priorities and contra-indications for COVID-19 vaccinations.	https://endo-ern.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/20210205_summary_ERN_COVID-19_Vaccination_updated20210212.pdf
ERN-LUNG	Online expert advisory platform	Expert Advisory Board EXABO.	https://exabo-lung.mig-frankfurt.de/archive
ERN-RND	Webinar	1. Webinar “COVID-19 and rare diseases” 2. Webinar on Huntington’s disease & COVID-19	1. https://www.ern-rnd.eu/28-january-2021-webinar-covid-19-and-rare-diseases/ 2. https://www.ern-rnd.eu/recording-of-webinar-on-huntingtons-disease-covid-19-available/
ERN-Skin	Recommendations	1. Patients with rare skin diseases and COVID-19 virus. 2. Vaccination advice.	1. https://ern-skin.eu/covid-19/ 2. https://ern-skin.eu/vaccination-advice/
VASCERN	List of resources	COVID	https://vascern.eu/?s=covid&post_type=&date

Supplementary table 2. Overview of documents developed by European Reference Networks in response to the war in Ukraine.

ERN	Type	Title	Link
Endo-ERN	Statement	Ukraine and endocrine drug shortages: joint statement from the Ukrainian Diabetology Association, the Association of the Endocrinologists of Ukraine, and the European Society of Endocrinology.	https://www.es-e-hormones.org/media/1s0ipjsa/statement-ukraine-drug-shortages-22march2022-v3.pdf
ERKNet	Support	Solidarity with Ukraine #ERNcare4Ua.	https://www.erknet.org/news/solidarity-with-ukraine
ERN eUROGEN	Webinar	Webinar programme.	https://eurogen-ern.eu/webinars/webinar-programme/
ERN EURO-NMD	Congress presentation	Landscape of gene therapy practices across Europe.	https://ern-euro-nmd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Landscape-of-gene-therapy-practices-5Mar.pdf
ERN PaedCan	Recommendations	The impact of the war in Ukraine on oncology patients: overview and recommendations for European and Ukrainian health authorities and policymakers.	https://efpia.eu/media/677308/efpia-the-impact-of-the-war-in-ukraine-on-oncology-patients_final.pdf
ERN PaedCan	Support	Ukrainian children living with cancer transferred to Germany from damaged Kyiv paediatric hospital.	https://www.who.int/europe/news/item/19-07-2024-ukrainian-children-living-with-cancer-transferred-to-germany-from-damaged-kyiv-paediatric-hospital
ERN PaedCan	Collaborations	1. Tabletochki: about us. 2. St. Jude Children’s Research Hospital supports Ukraine cancer patients. 3. Childhood Cancer International (CCI) Europe: safe passage out of Ukraine.	1. https://tabletochki.org/en/foundation/ 2. https://www.stjude.org/about-st-jude/60-minutes-ukraine-segment.html 3. https://ccieurope.eu/ukraine/
ERN PaedCan	Peer-reviewed publications	1. Caring for children with cancer evacuated from Ukraine: The patients’ perception. ²⁶ 2. The impact of armed conflict on global patterns of childhood cancer. ²⁷ 3. Psychosocial Impact of the War in Ukraine on Pediatric Cancer Patients and Their Families Receiving Oncological Care Outside Their Country at the Onset of Hostilities. ²⁸ 4. Global effort to evacuate Ukrainian children with cancer and blood disorders who have been affected by war. ²⁹	1. https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.31087 2. https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(24)00559-X 3. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adro.2022.100957 4. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-3026(22)00259-9

		5. Evacuating Patients With Pediatric Cancer From Ukraine: Impact on Medical Care Capacity in Poland. ³⁰ 6. Development of a centralised triage centre for children with cancer and blood disorders in response to the humanitarian crisis in Ukraine. ³¹	5. https://doi.org/10.1200/GO.24.00046 6. https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(23)00456-4
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Support	ERN-EuroBloodNet Patients Assistance Infopoint.	https://eurobloodnet.eu/cross-border-health/ern-eurobloodnet-patients-assistance-infopoint/
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Collaboration	Ukraine's patients association for paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria (PNH).	https://pnh.org.ua/
ERN-EYE (coordinator)	Statement	Statement to support people with rare diseases and complex conditions affected by the war in Ukraine.	https://ern-lung.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Statement-ERNcare4ua-14-March-2022-2.pdf
ERN-EYE (coordinator)	Website	#ERNcare4Ua Rare Diseases Doctors.	https://www.erncare4ua.com/
ERN-EYE (coordinator)	Peer-reviewed publication	The European Reference Networks for rare and complex diseases respond to the Ukrainian crisis. ³²	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2022.100464
ERN-LUNG	Webinar + on-site training	ERN-LUNG Academy.	https://ern-lung.eu/our-expertise/education/ern-lung-academy/

Supplementary table 3. Overview of documents developed by European Reference Networks in response to other crises.

ERN	Type	Title	Link
ERN Collaboration	Peer-reviewed publication	Mapping the rare disease paediatric clinical trial availabilities in Europe. ³³	https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2025.1523847
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Congress presentation	SCD recommendations in the EU: a EuroBloodNet review of national implementation, gaps, and research priorities.	https://ascatconferences.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/ASCAT-2025-Accepted-Abstract-Submissions.pdf
ERN-EuroBloodNet	Regulatory collaboration	The AEMPS reports the supply of Hydrea 500 mg through the application of Medicines in Special Situations.	https://www.aemps.gob.es/informa/la-aemps-informa-del-suministro-de-hydrea-500-mg-a-traves-de-la-aplicacion-de-medicamentos-en-situaciones-especiales/

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